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Education in the Global Innovation Index

Decreased by 0.79% between 2013 and 2022

The "Education" indicator of the Global Innovation Index (GII) is crucial for evaluating a country's ability to sustain and promote innovation through its education system. This indicator measures various aspects, including access to primary and secondary education, considering the percentage of children and adolescents enrolled in respective schools. The quality of education is assessed through the student-teacher ratio and students' performance in international standardized tests like PISA. Additionally, it examines the enrollment rate in tertiary education and the quality of universities and research institutions, measured through rankings and international reputation. The indicator also includes lifelong learning and continuous education, with a particular focus on vocational training opportunities and policies supporting continuous learning. Equity in education is another critical aspect, analyzing gender disparities and access to education for disadvantaged groups such as minorities and students with disabilities. Investments in education are evaluated in terms of public expenditure on education and per-student spending, reflecting the government's priority in this sector. Finally, educational infrastructure, including the availability of resources such as libraries and science labs, is considered to determine the overall quality of the education system. In summary, the "Education" indicator of the GII provides a comprehensive view of a country's education system, highlighting both strengths and areas needing improvement to support and stimulate innovation.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+24>

Education in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data on education within the 2022 Global Innovation Index (GII) show a wide range of scores among different countries, highlighting significant disparities in access to and quality of global education. At the top of the list is Botswana with an impressive score of 87.6, followed by Namibia with 73.7. These scores likely reflect a strong commitment in terms of resources and policies to improve the education system in these African countries, which could be a key element for their economic and innovative development. Among European countries, Norway and Sweden stand out with scores of 72.4 and 72.1, respectively. These results are not surprising, considering these countries' reputation for their excellent and well-funded education systems, characterized by universal access and a strong emphasis on quality education. Belgium and Iceland also show high scores (70.6 and 70.4), confirming the importance attributed to education as a pillar for innovation. China, with a score of 69.3, highlights its ongoing effort to improve the education system, which is an integral part of its strategy to become a global innovation powerhouse. Nordic countries like Denmark and Finland (68.9 and 68.4, respectively) continue to demonstrate high educational standards, supporting their reputation as leaders in innovation.

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Interestingly, countries like Oman (66.2), New Zealand (65.5), and Cyprus (65.4) rank higher than technologically advanced countries like South Korea (65.1) and Hong Kong SAR, China (64.3). These results can be attributed to targeted educational policies and significant investments in educational infrastructure and resources. Countries like Tunisia (65), Belarus (64.1), and Portugal (63.7) are relatively high-ranked, indicating a good level of education that can support further innovative developments. Notably, countries like Germany (62.2) and Canada (62) are not at the top, although they remain above the global average, reflecting robust education systems but also the need for continued innovation to maintain global competitiveness. In contrast, countries like the United States (58.6) and the United Kingdom (59.7), traditionally seen as leaders in higher education, appear lower than expected. This could reflect internal challenges in their education systems, such as disparities in access to quality education and high costs of higher education. In the middle and lower end of the ranking, countries like Vietnam (55.1), Brazil (51.4), and South Africa (50) have scores indicating education systems with significant areas for improvement. These scores suggest that, although there have been progress, substantial challenges persist in ensuring universal access to quality education. Countries like Bangladesh (18.8), Mauritania (18.4), and Uganda (16.1) are among the last in the ranking. These low scores indicate severe deficiencies in the education system, which can include inadequate infrastructure, low quality of teaching, and limited access to education. The implications of these scores are profound, as a weak education system seriously hinders a country's ability to develop skilled human capital, essential for innovation and economic development. Examining the data as a whole, it is clear that countries with high scores in education tend to also possess strong innovation ecosystems. This is consistent with the theory that a robust education system is fundamental for developing the skills needed for innovation. In this context, countries with high scores show that significant investments in education yield long-term benefits for their ability to innovate and compete globally. For countries with lower scores, the data highlight the urgent need for educational reforms and investments to improve access and quality of education. However, improving education in these countries is not an easy task and requires strategic interventions addressing a variety of challenges, including poverty, social inequalities, and the lack of adequate infrastructure. In summary, the education indicator of the 2022 Global Innovation Index offers a detailed overview of the educational capacities of various countries, highlighting both successes and critical areas for improvement. A strong and inclusive education system emerges as a determining factor for a country's innovative potential, directly influencing its ability to compete in the global economy.

Education in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022. The data on education in the Global Innovation Index (GII) from 2013 to 2022 highlight significant trends and changes in different countries. Analyzing the scores, it emerges that some countries have significantly improved their educational performance, while others have declined. This analysis allows for a better understanding of global educational dynamics and their impact on innovation. Botswana is an example of remarkable improvement, rising from 62.5 in 2013 to 87.6 in 2022. This increase could be attributed to more effective educational policies and greater investment in the education sector. Another African country that has seen significant improvement is Namibia, which has risen from 51.2 to 73.7. These progressions indicate that some African nations are successfully investing in education to stimulate innovation. In Europe, Norway has seen a slight decrease from 66.5 to 72.4, while Sweden has maintained a relatively stable position, moving from 71.5 to 72.1. This suggests that despite small variations, Nordic countries continue to maintain a high level of educational quality, crucial for sustaining their position as leaders in innovation. A significant decline is observable in countries like Belgium and Iceland. Belgium has dropped from 72.9 to 70.6, while Iceland from 77.4 to 70.4. These data could reflect economic challenges or changes in educational policies that have negatively

impacted the sector. China has shown a slight increase from 68.7 to 69.3, indicating a consistent commitment to education, which is a fundamental pillar of its technological and innovative development strategy. Other Asian countries like South Korea and Hong Kong have shown improvements, respectively from 59 to 65.1 and from 51.7 to 64.3, demonstrating the importance Asia places on education as a means to stimulate innovation. In the Middle East, Oman has improved its score from 44.5 to 66.2, reflecting significant investments in education to diversify the economy and reduce dependency on natural resources. Conversely, countries like Kuwait and Qatar have shown only marginal or stable improvements, suggesting that there may be further opportunities to improve education in these regions. Among Latin American countries, Costa Rica has seen an improvement, rising from 53.6 to 58.2, while others like Argentina and Brazil have recorded declines. Argentina has dropped from 58 to 42.5 and Brazil from 51 to 51.4, indicating potential challenges in maintaining a strong education system that can support innovation. In Africa, Mauritius is noteworthy, with a significant increase from 38.9 to 60.9. This indicates a strong commitment to improving education, which is essential for economic growth and innovation. However, other African countries like Ghana and South Africa have shown less marked progress or even declines, signaling the need for further reforms and investments in the sector. Some countries have seen notable reductions, such as Ireland, which has fallen from 78.4 to 48.6, and Japan, from 66.7 to 56.5. These declines could be attributed to various factors, including demographic, economic, or political changes that have negatively impacted the education system. Conversely, some countries have maintained a stable level or slightly improved, such as Vietnam, which has moved from 56.8 to 55.1. This suggests that despite difficulties, there have been efforts to maintain and improve the education system. In conclusion, the Global Innovation Index data on education show a varied landscape with countries significantly improving, others maintaining stability, and some facing substantial challenges. Positive trends in countries like Botswana, Namibia, and Oman demonstrate that investment in education can lead to great benefits in terms of innovation and economic development. However, declines observed in countries like Belgium, Iceland, and Ireland highlight that even advanced nations must continually adapt and improve their educational policies to remain competitive in the knowledge-based global economy. These results underline the critical importance of education as a key factor for innovation and sustainable development.

Conclusions. The average value of education within the Global Innovation Index decreased by 0.79% between 2013 and 2022. There are countries where the value of education in the Global Innovation Index has grown far more than the average value, such as Pakistan with 286.42%, Zambia with 214.89%, Zimbabwe with 202.27%, Nigeria with 81.64%, and Mozambique with +59.86%. However, there are countries where the average value of education within the Global Innovation Index has significantly decreased, such as Ireland with -38.01%, Jordan with -38.225, Ecuador with -39.56%, Yemen with -40.00%, and Uganda with -53.33%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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